

A Deep Learning Approach for Automated Constraint Network Generalization

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Abstract. Constraint acquisition (CA) methods learn constraint models from examples of solutions and (usually) non-solutions, to automate the difficult task of mathematical modelling. Most CA methods learn constraints for problems of a certain size from examples of that size, but a few can learn from examples of other sizes. Recent work has decomposed this task into (i) learning models of multiple fixed sizes, and (ii) extrapolating these to other sizes. This has the advantage that fixed-size models can be learned by any convenient CA method. In this paper, we a) propose ExCON, a novel, more automated approach (than current methods) for constraint network generalization, b) provide empirical evidence of ExCON’s performance on five diverse CA benchmarks, c) compare ExCON with state-of-the-art CSP generalization methods, and d) evaluate ExCON under different noise settings. ExCON is designed to generalize constraint models of unseen sizes by learning from multiple fixed-size instances in a more automated manner. We demonstrate that ExCON performs accurately on this task and shows competitive performance with an approach based on classifiers with feature engineering.

Keywords: Constraint Acquisition · CSP Generalization · Deep Learning

1 Introduction

Constraint Programming (CP) provides powerful modelling languages and solvers for constrained optimization and decision making problems. A constraint satisfaction problem (CSP) consists of a set of variables, each with a domain of possible values, and a network of constraints each defined on a subset of variables. Modelling a new application as a CSP requires expertise, which can hinder the uptake of constraint programming (CP). Constraint Acquisition (CA) methods aim to automate the challenging task of mathematical modeling by learning constraint models from examples of solutions—and typically non-solutions.

Most CA methods learn constraint models of CSPs of fixed sizes from instances of that size [9, 8, 18, 21, 22, 24–26, 29, 27, 33]. For example, they learn constraints for an 8-queens problem from a dataset of 8-queens solutions (and possibly non-solutions depending on the method). Although many real-world applications require CA methods to handle instances of varying sizes [13]. Model

Seeker [1] is a method that can take input solutions of varying sizes (such as 3,4, and 5-queens) and learn a CSP of a different size (8-queens). Another approach is to use Inductive Logic Programming to learn a generalized constraint model [20]. This generalized form of CA has wider applicability than the usual fixed-size methods but is also a more challenging problem (problem size is not the only kind of parameter that can be generalised).

Recent work has decomposed the generalization task into (i) learning models of multiple fixed sizes and (ii) extrapolating these to other sizes. This has the advantage that fixed-size models can be learned by any convenient CA method, and their common underlying patterns can be exploited to infer constraints for new, larger instances. Two notable approaches address the challenge of generalizing constraint models. In [28], the extrapolation problem is reformulated as a symbolic classification task and uses genetic programming to infer mathematical expressions that separate valid constraints (1) from invalid ones (0). This approach perfectly learns constraint models in smaller instances and generalizes well to larger, unseen ones. However, reliance on genetic programming incurs high computational costs. Another approach to generalizing CSP constraint models is GENCON [31]. It trains a classifier on parameterized feature representations of individual constraints, then extracts decision rules from interpretable, generalized constraint specifications. These specifications can be generalized to larger problem sizes. However, this method depends on manual feature engineering, which may hinder its applicability in broader applications, as it demands user expertise. Specifically, GENCON’s feature engineering pipeline consists of four handcrafted components: relation features encode the constraint type via one-hot vectors, flag whether any constant appears, and store each constant’s value as a separate feature; partitioning features introduce binary indicators for all tensor and latent dimensions. This is discovered by checking which problem parameters divide each tensor size; conditioning features include numerical summaries such as the average difference of variable indices along each dimension. This encodes sequence or distance-based constraints within each variable group; and parameter mapping replaces each raw constant value with the name of its originating problem parameter (or NaN if it does not have any). The classifier can then learn from parameter identities rather than raw numbers only.

Unlike GENCON, which uses handcrafted features, ExCON is more automated. It takes as input each candidate constraint’s raw instance tuple, combines it with the instance parameters, and accurately predicts constraint models. This paper makes the following contributions:

- We introduce ExCON, a more automated approach (than current methods) to constraint network generalization. ExCON learns constraint models from multiple fixed-size CSP instances and applies the learned rules to unseen instances of other sizes.
- We show how to generate data for CSPs and demonstrate this with an example.

- We evaluate ExCON under interpolation and extrapolation data distributions. We further compare ExCON’s performance to standard classifiers using k-fold cross-validation.
- We provide empirical evidence of ExCON’s comparable performance to state-of-the-art (SOTA) methods on five diverse CSP benchmarks by performing a 10-fold cross-validation.
- We show that ExCON’s performance remains robust under different levels of noise settings.
- We show that ExCON’s performance gains are statistically significant compared to standard classifier baselines.

2 Constraint Network Generalization

Related Work - A major bottleneck in the adoption of CP is modeling [32]. Expressing a combinatorial problem as a set of constraints over decision variables requires significant expertise [12]. Traditional CA methods are mainly categorized into passive (learning from a dataset of solutions and usually nonsolutions) and active (interactively learning by querying an oracle or user). These methods typically learn ground constraints for a single instance. Early approaches included interactive systems, such as the matchmaker agent [14], which incrementally gathered missing constraints from the user when incorrect solutions were produced. Other approaches relied on version space methods (based on the classical version space paradigm [23, 15]) such as CONACQ1 [4] which learns complete constraint networks from a dataset of positive and negative examples. Active approaches, such as CONACQ2 [5], extend these methods to learn through complete membership queries by first asking the user to classify the generated examples as solutions or non-solutions. It then uses this as feedback to iteratively refine the candidate constraint network. Techniques such as ModelSeeker [1] exploit problem structure to learn global constraints from positive examples, while systems such as QuAcq [3] reduce query overhead by actively posing partial queries. Recognizing that a negative example may violate multiple constraints, MultiACQ [21] was proposed to extract complete minimal scopes corresponding to the violated constraints of a single negative example.

Gap in the literature - Achieving the same ability to generalize constraint models of different instances of the same problem has been a key challenge for CA [30]. Traditional CA approaches have significant limitations because they can only learn constraint models of instances of fixed sizes [2, 7]. Classifier-based ML approaches have evolved from early symbolic and statistical techniques to address this challenge. However, only a few of these methods support generalization (accurately extending learned rules to unseen sizes of the same problem) [28, 11]. GENCON and related techniques (those based on inductive logic programming [20], or Count-CP [19]) depend heavily on manual feature engineering and predefined variable partitions. This dependency requires domain expertise and restricts the idea of automated modeling. This can limit their use across different domains.

Significance - Real-world CSPs are not static and often vary in scale or structure as the underlying parameters change. For example, consider a university scheduling problem where a constraint network modeled for a small exam timetable in one department must be applied to a larger timetable covering multiple departments, with more courses, rooms, and timeslots. Most CA systems would be confined to the original instance size, as only a few generalize to larger instances. Without the ability to extrapolate, the learned model is severely restricted, greatly limiting its practical use. Hence, constraint network generalization is crucial for many real-world challenges involving CSPs. By generalizing the learned constraints to unseen larger problem instances, we can build models that adapt to evolving requirements and enhance the robustness of CA methods.

2.1 Notations and Definitions

Definition 1 (Constraint Satisfaction Problem). A constraint satisfaction problem (CSP) is a triple $P = (V, D, C)$, defining:

- a set of n decision variables $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$, representing the entities of the problem,
- a set of n domains $D = \{D_{v_1}, D_{v_2}, \dots, D_{v_n}\}$, with $D_{v_i} \subset Z$ being the domain of $v_i \in V$,
- a constraint set $C = \{c_1, \dots, c_t\}$ over the variables in V .

A constraint c is a pair $(\text{rel}(c), \text{var}(c))$, where $\text{var}(c) \subset V$ is the scope of the constraint, and $\text{rel}(c)$ is a relation over the domains of the variables in $\text{var}(c)$, restricting their allowed value assignments. The arity of the constraint, denoted $|\text{var}(c)| = \text{arity}(\text{rel}(c))$, indicates the number of variables involved. The set of solutions of a constraint set C is denoted by $\text{sol}(C)$.

Notation In a CSP, a constraint language Γ defines a finite set of relations $\{R_1, \dots, R_k\}$ over D such that every constraint in C applies one of $R_i \in \Gamma$ to a subset of variables V .

Let $C^+ = \{c_i \mid c_i \in C\}$, $C^- = \{c_i \mid c_i \notin C\}$. C denotes the true constraint set of a problem instance.

Definition 2 (Candidate Constraint). In a CSP defined by the triple (V, D, C) , a candidate constraint is a (unordered) subset of V whose scope matches the constraint language Γ but which may or may not belong to the true constraint set C . We denote the full set of candidates by bias $B_A = \{v \subseteq V \mid \text{scope}(c) \in \Gamma\}$, also denoted as $B_A = C^+ \cup C^-$.

Definition 3 (Parameterised CSP Instance). Let a CSP be defined by a parameter set $S = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_q\}$ and a function mapping each parameter instantiation $P = \{(p_1, u_1), (p_2, u_2), \dots, (p_q, u_q)\}$ onto a ground CSP defined on (V, D, C) . The resulting tuple (P, V, D, C) is then defined as a parameterised CSP instance.

An instance refers to a parameterised CSP instance defined in 3.

Definition 4 (Constraint Network Generalization). *Given a parameterised CSP instance (P, V, D, C) , let P_{train} and P_{test} denote disjoint sets of parameter instantiations of training and testing instances respectively, i.e., $P_{test} \cap P_{train} = \emptyset$. Let f_θ be a learned function on m problem instances $\{(P^i, V^i, D^i, C^i)\}_{i=1}^m$ with $P^i \in P_{train}$. For any test instance (P^*, V^*, D^*, C^*) with $P^* \in P_{test}$, let $BA(f_\theta; P^*)$ denote the balanced accuracy computed over that instance. We say that f_θ generalizes to any test instance $(P^*, V^*, D^*, C^*) | P^* \in P_{test}$ if $BA(f_\theta; P^*) \geq \tau$, $\tau > 0.90$*

We use the terms constraint network generalization and generalization interchangeably in the rest of the paper.

Definition 5 (Machine Learning Task). *Given a training set $E = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N \subset R^d \times \{0, 1\}$, where $(x, y) \in D_{P_{train}}$ (denoting distribution of training instances), the objective is to learn a function $f_\theta : R^d \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$, with learnable parameters θ , to minimize a loss function $L(f_\theta(x), y)$ measuring the error between the predicted and the true class labels.*

Definition 6 (Problem Statement). *Given m parameterised CSP problem instances $\{(P^i, V^i, D^i, C^i)\}_{i=1}^m$, the objective of generalization is to learn a function $F : (P, V, D) \mapsto C$ such that, for any target instance with vocabulary (V^*, D^*) defined by parameter instantiation $P^* = \{(p_1, u_1^*), (p_2, u_2^*), \dots, (p_q, u_q^*)\}$, $F(P^*, V^*, D^*)$ returns the true constraint set C^* . That is, we learn F from the given ground CSPs $\{(P^i, V^i, D^i, C^i)\}_{i=1}^m$ so that F predicts the correct C^* for any (P^*, V^*, D^*) .*

3 Methodology

3.1 Dataset Generation

We follow an approach similar to [31] and build the dataset at the constraint level, i.e., where each example corresponds to an individual candidate constraint. For a given parameterised CSP instance, we define a set of candidate constraints $C^+ \in C$ (part of the true constraint model) and a distinct set of constraints $C_A^- \notin C$ (constraints that are not part of the true model). In practice, we may only have access to the set of true constraints C^+ for each problem instance. However, we also need a set of candidate constraints C^- that would produce a negative label to train a classifier model. We produce this set by first generating a candidate constraint set B_A using a constraint language Γ . This is a collection of all relations in C^+ (such as row, column, and block constraints in Sudoku), i.e., $\Gamma = \{rel(c) | c \in C^+\}$. We then apply it to all possible variable scopes observed in the instance. Finally, the set C^- consists of all constraints in B_A that are not part of the given instance(s), i.e., $C_A^- = B_A \setminus C_A$. The complete candidate space is defined as $C^+ \cup C^-$. For all $c \in C^+$ we assign a label 1 and 0 otherwise.

3.2 Running Example: Sudoku

Consider a 9×9 Sudoku puzzle parameterised by (n, b_r, b_c) divided into $n(=9) \times 3 \times 3$ blocks, $b_r = b_c = 3$, where b_r and b_c denote the block height and block width dimensions respectively. The goal is to complete the puzzle in such a way that all rows, columns, and non-overlapping $b_r \times b_c$ blocks contain distinct numbers from 1 to 9. The instance parameters are (n, b_r, b_c) . The variables are the grid cells, $V = \{v_{i,j} \mid 1 \leq i, j \leq 9\}$, and domains the different values they can take, $D = \{1, 2, \dots, 9\}$ of each $v_{i,j}$. A candidate constraint is any unordered pair of two distinct grid variables that could be subject to a \neq constraint. We enumerate over all index pairs $(i, j), (i', j')$ in domain D to form the bias (the set of all candidate constraints) $B_A = \{\{v_{i,j}, v_{i',j'}\} \mid 1 \leq i, j \leq n, 1 \leq i', j' \leq n, (i, j) < (i', j')\}$. The final feature vector for each candidate constraint $c \in B_A$ is defined by appending the instance parameters (n, b_r, b_c) to the individual variable cell coordinates $v_{i,j} = (i, j)$, and $v_{i',j'} = (i', j')$, i.e., $\varphi_\sigma(c, P) = \langle n, b_r, b_c, i, j, i', j' \rangle$. This encoding makes each candidate constraint (across all instances) represented using a fixed-length feature vector (making it size-agnostic). Using definition 5, a classifier f_θ is trained on all examples of a 9×9 sudoku (3240 candidate constraints) of the form $\varphi_\sigma(c, P)$. We then generate a new problem instance, say a 16×16 Sudoku with parameters $P^* = \{16, 4, 4\}$, apply f_θ to all examples of this instance, and compute the balanced accuracy (BA) on the test instance. The generalization task is to extend the learned rules of a constraint type to larger (or unseen) instances of the same type. In practice, we aggregate the feature-label pairs from multiple training instances into one dataset and individually test on several held-out test instances to more robustly assess the classifier’s generalization on a problem class.

The pipeline, from data generation to evaluation, is completely automated for ExCON. The user inputs only the instance parameters to define the instance (s). Further steps, such as pre-processing, training, and evaluation are automated.

4 Experiments

4.1 Evaluation Metrics

We evaluate using two performance metrics: balanced accuracy (primary metric), the mean of sensitivity and specificity. It gives an accurate measure of each class, and is appropriate for highly imbalanced data; and F1-score (secondary metric), which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall.

4.2 Hypotheses

We define and evaluate our hypotheses using our primary metric, balanced accuracy (BA). Given a parameterised CSP instance defined by $P = \{(p_1, u_1), (p_2, u_2), \dots, (p_q, u_q)\}$, we define the hypotheses as follows:

Hypothesis 1 (Standard Classifier Comparison) Let $P_{\text{test}} = \{p^* \notin P_{\text{train}}\}$ denote the held-out test instances of a parameterised CSP, and let $\mathcal{C} =$

Fig. 1: ExCON architecture. Instance parameters and coordinate features are concatenated and passed through three hidden layers (Linear \rightarrow ReLU \rightarrow Dropout). The output layer produces a logit; sigmoid is applied at inference. Training uses a two-phase loss: BCE warm-up (50 epochs), then α -soft-F1 + $(1-\alpha)$ -BCE. Optimisation uses Adam with cosine annealing and gradient clipping. A decision threshold is calibrated post-training by maximising F1 on the training set via a sweep over $[0, 1]$. The calibrated threshold fixed on the training set is used to evaluate the model on all test instances.

$\{\text{RF, kNN, XGB}\}$ be the set of standard classifiers, such that $\text{BA}_{\max}(\mathcal{C}; p^*)$ be the highest balanced accuracy achieved by \mathcal{C} for all $p^* \in P_{\text{test}}$. We hypothesize that ExCON achieves a balanced accuracy higher than any classifier in \mathcal{C} . That is, $\forall p^* \in P_{\text{test}} : \text{BA}(f_{\text{ExCON}}; p^*) \geq \text{BA}_{\max}(\mathcal{C}; p^*) - \delta_1$.

Hypothesis 2 (Generalization to Interpolation and Extrapolation Instances) Let $P_{\text{test}}^{\text{in}} = \{p^* \notin P_{\text{train}} \mid \forall j \in \{1, \dots, q\} : \min_{p \in P_{\text{train}}} p_j \leq p_j^* \leq \max_{p \in P_{\text{train}}} p_j\}$. Let $P_{\text{test}}^{\text{out}} = \{p^* \notin P_{\text{train}} \mid \forall j \in \{1, \dots, q\} : p_j^* > \max_{p \in P_{\text{train}}} p_j \vee p_j^* < \min_{p \in P_{\text{train}}} p_j\}$. We hypothesize that the learned function f_θ generalizes successfully to all interpolation instances, that is, $\forall p^* \in P_{\text{test}}^{\text{in}} : \text{BA}(f_\theta; p^*) \geq \tau$, $\tau > 0.90$ and to all extrapolation instances $\forall p^* \in P_{\text{test}}^{\text{out}} : \text{BA}(f_\theta; p^*) \geq \tau$, $\tau > 0.90$ ¹

Hypothesis 3 (State-of-the-Art Comparison) Let $P_{\text{test}} = \{p^* \notin P_{\text{train}}\}$ denote the held-out test instances of a parameterised CSP and let $\mathcal{S} = \{\text{GenCON, Count-CP}\}$ denote the the set of state-of-the-art generalization methods such that $\text{BA}_{\max}(\mathcal{S}; p^*)$ and $\text{BA}_{\min}(\mathcal{S}; p^*)$ denote the highest and lowest BA achieved by a method in \mathcal{S} . We hypothesize that for a small tolerance $\delta_2 \geq 0$,

$\forall p^* \in P_{\text{test}} : \text{BA}_{\min}(\mathcal{S}; p^*) - \delta_2 \leq \text{BA}(f_{\text{ExCON}}; p^*) \leq \text{BA}_{\max}(\mathcal{S}; p^*) + \delta_2$. i.e, ExCON’s balanced accuracy is *competitive* within this range — it does not exceed the best by more than δ_2 , nor falls below the worst by more than δ_2

Hypothesis 4 (Noise Robustness) Let $\{\eta_1 < \eta_2 < \dots < \eta_L\}$ denote an increasing progression of noise levels induced for all training instances of a parameterised CSP $p \in P_{\text{train}}$ and let f_θ^η denote the ExCON model trained on noise level η . We then define $\text{BA}(\eta) := \text{BA}(f_\theta^\eta; p^*)$ as the balanced accuracy at

¹ 0.90 is obtained by evaluating SOTA methods on the benchmarks, and is thus considered a good standard for defining generalisation accuracy for ExCON.

Classifier	BA	F ₁
ExCON	0.98 (± 0.02)	0.97 (± 0.02)
RF	0.94 (± 0.03)	0.89 (± 0.08)
KNN	0.92 (± 0.07)	0.86 (± 0.14)
XGB	0.87 (± 0.09)	0.82 (± 0.10)

Table 1: Overall performance (mean \pm std) averaged over all benchmarks.

Problem	Interpolation BA	Extrapolation BA
Nqueens	1.00 (± 0.00)	0.97 (± 0.03)
Latin Squares	1.00 (± 0.00)	0.98 (± 0.02)
Sudoku	0.94 (± 0.01)	0.92 (± 0.01)
Exam Timetabling	0.99 (± 0.00)	0.96 (± 0.04)
Nurse Rostering	0.98 (± 0.05)	0.94 (± 0.07)

Table 2: Balanced accuracy on interpolation and extrapolation instances (mean \pm std) per benchmark.

noise η , and hypothesize that there exists a threshold $\eta^* \geq 0$, such that for all $\eta \leq \eta^* \forall p^* \in P_{\text{test}} : |\text{BA}(f_{\theta}^{\eta}; p^*) - \text{BA}(f_{\theta}^0; p^*)| \leq \delta$ i.e., ExCON’s balanced accuracy remains consistent (within δ) for noise up to η^* .

4.3 Benchmarks and Hyperparameter Optimisation

We use five well-known CA benchmarks - Nqueens, Latin Squares, Sudoku, Exam Timetabling, and Nurse Rostering. We generate data for each benchmark by defining a range of parameters, and randomly select values in that range. For example, we select N between 7 and 50 in Nqueens. We perform a Bayesian Hyperparameter Optimization (B-HPO) for all classifiers using a tree-based Parzen estimator surrogate that models a relationship between the hyperparameter configurations and the F1-scores. We then apply a percentile-pruning strategy at intermediate epochs to cut down the runtime. We generate 20 instances, use 10 for training and 10 for testing. We run 50 optimization trials for each model and benchmark. We run 50 optimization trials for each model and benchmark. For ExCON we tune: learning rate, l2 weight decay, hidden layer sizes, dropout, and α .

4.4 K-fold Cross-Validation

We evaluate ExCON’s generalization abilities by generating a set of 10 instances (all different from those used for B-HPO) for each benchmark. We then run 10-fold cross-validation experiments for each classifier on each benchmark by selecting 6 instances at random for training, and testing on the remaining 4 instances in each fold. We set the same seed for all classifiers on a benchmark. We compute the aggregated BA and F1 values for each fold per benchmark. Table 1 shows the overall performance of classifiers aggregated across all benchmarks. ExCON achieves a higher BA than other classifiers. This supports hypothesis 1.

4.5 Interpolation and Extrapolation Properties

For each benchmark, we generate four training instances, four interpolation instances, and six extrapolation instances (two smaller than the minimum training instance size and four larger than the maximum training instance size). We report average results on interpolation and extrapolation instances in Table 2. Due

Method	BA	F ₁
ExCON	0.99	0.97
GenCON	0.98	0.98
Count-CP	0.97	0.97

Table 3: Average performance across five benchmarks.

Fig. 2: Balanced accuracy across five benchmarks.

to space limitations, we only report the BA scores. For $\tau = 0.90$, we show that $\forall p^* \in P_{\text{test}}^{\text{in}} : \text{BA}(f_{\theta}; p^*) \geq \tau$, and $\forall p^* \in P_{\text{test}}^{\text{out}} : \text{BA}(f_{\theta}; p^*) \geq \tau$. This supports hypothesis 2.

4.6 Evaluating against SOTA

We use the same set of 10 instances generated for our cross-validation experiments and run 10-fold cross-validation on ExCON, GenCON, and Count-CP. We train on 6 instances and test on the remaining 4 in each fold. We set a unique seed per benchmark for all methods to ensure they train and test on the same instances in each fold. We used existing implementations of SOTA methods from [11]. Figure ?? depicts BA for all methods on five benchmarks. For $\delta_2 = 0.2$ we note that $\text{BA}(f_{\text{ExCON}}; p^*) \leq \text{BA}_{\text{max}}(\mathcal{S}; p^*) + \delta_2$ holds true. Hence, we show competitive performance to SOTA. This supports hypothesis 3.

4.7 Impact of Noise

We evaluate ExCON’s robustness by defining false-positive (FP) noise as flipping a percentage of negative labels to positive, and false-negative (FN) noise as flipping a percentage of positive labels to negative. FP noise injects spurious constraints in the dataset and FN noise drops actual constraints from the true model. We perform 10-fold cross validation for training (6 instances) and testing (4 instances). Due to space limitations, we present the primary metric BA against noise injection.

Table 4 shows that ExCON is robust up to 20% FP and FN noise respectively. Let $\eta^* = 0.20$ and $\delta = 0.03$. We show that for any $\eta \leq \eta^*$ and $\forall p^* \in P_{\text{test}}$: $|\text{BA}(f_{\theta}^{\eta}; p^*) - \text{BA}(f_{\theta}^0; p^*)| \leq \delta$. ExCON shows robust and consistent performance on noisy data. This supports Hypothesis 4.

4.8 Statistical Significance Tests

We evaluate statistical significance using standard non-parametric tests used to compare classifiers over multiple datasets [10]. We used: 1. Friedman’s test measure with Iman–Davenport correction [17], 2. Nemenyi’s post-hoc test for pairwise ranking [10], and 3. Wilcoxon signed-rank test with Bonferroni correction [6, 16] to compare ExCON against each baseline. For each benchmark, we ran five independent trials (each with a different random seed) and within each trial we performed a 10-fold cross-validation (6 for training, 4 for testing, train/test sets being disjoint in each fold). We averaged the BA scores on 50 observation points per classifier per benchmark, ensuring enough samples for statistical tests and enough data to study variability between folds and across seeds.

Across all benchmarks, test (1) strongly rejected the null hypothesis of all classifiers being equivalent in performance ($p \ll 0.001$), and test (3) confirmed significant pairwise differences ($p_{\text{adj}} < 0.001$). Due to space limitations, we only show the results from test (2) in (Table 5).

5 Conclusion

Most CA methods learn fixed-size CSPs from instances of the same size. We present ExCON, a more automated deep learning based approach to generalize constraint models to unseen CSP instances. We report results on five CA benchmarks and compare performance against SOTA. Current SOTA like GenCON and Count-CP are robust CSP generalization methods, but rely heavily on feature engineering that demands user expertise in a real-world scenario. ExCON’s

Noise (%)	FP BA	FN BA
0	0.94 (± 0.07)	0.96 (± 0.04)
5	0.96 (± 0.04)	0.96 (± 0.02)
10	0.97 (± 0.03)	0.97 (± 0.02)
15	0.96 (± 0.03)	0.96 (± 0.02)
20	0.97 (± 0.02)	0.95 (± 0.01)

Table 4: Impact of false-positive (FP) and false-negative (FN) noise on balanced accuracy (BA), aggregated across problem classes.

Benchmark	ExCON	RF	XGB	KNN
N-Queens	1.2	2.5	3.4	3.5
Latin Squares	1.0	2.0	3.4	3.6
Sudoku	1.0	2.7	3.2	3.1
Exam Timetabling	1.1	2.4	3.9	3.1
Nurse Rostering	1.3	3.5	1.8	3.5

Table 5: Average ranks of classifiers across benchmarks (lower is better). At $\alpha = 0.05$, Critical Difference (CD) in average ranks = 0.938. This shows ExCON’s statistically significant differences in performance compared to other baselines.

advantage lies in its increased automation while showing competitive performance with SOTA. However, this shifts the focus from feature engineering to HPO tasks. While more automated, ExCON takes longer for training and HPO tasks. Nevertheless, once trained and tuned, ExCON provides several benefits such as generalization to unseen instances (solves a critical problem in CA), noise robustness, and low inference times. Some areas of future work could be to optimize HPO runtimes, explore semi- and unsupervised learning CA paradigms, make ExCON fully automated (reduce reliance on problem parameters), and establish theoretical bounds for neural-network-based CSP generalization.

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